

Emotional Intelligence as a Relevant Factor in the Learning of Students in the Information Technology Area at the Polytechnic University of Tulancingo

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 05 September 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: María del Rosario López Torres</p>	<p>This research analyzes the impact of emotional intelligence (EI) on the learning process of higher education students. This study focuses on the areas of self-motivation, emotional control, interpersonal skills, and emotional counseling. This is due to the fact that students in Information Technology programs at the Polytechnic University of Tulancingo have exhibited boredom, tedium, and a hostile academic climate, resulting in poor academic results.</p> <p>The purpose of this research was to evaluate students' emotional intelligence to identify its impact on the learning process. The hypothesis is that self-awareness, emotional control, self-motivation, interpersonal relationships, and emotional counseling positively impact EI. The study used a quantitative, correlational, and explanatory approach with a longitudinal design.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Emotional intelligence, Behavior, Feelings, Self-awareness, Learning.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

The term emotion refers to a feeling, thoughts and an action, that is, emotions are immersed in all moments and in all behavior that the individual performs, as well as the fact that the alterations not only remain on the emotional side, but also interfere in the rational part [1]. In addition to the above, it has been identified that students in the area of Information Technologies at the Polytechnic University of Tulancingo (UPT) go through different emotions and each of them reacts differently to the stimuli they perceive, so that, by not knowing how to identify what emotions are present, they will not be able to have awareness about the acts that are carried out in their actions, so these actions can affect their academic development, the relationship with their classmates, teachers and the use of the different subjects. The lack of EI in them has caused decision-making to be affected and when participating in class they may choose to remain silent and not express their point of view, even if it is correct. In this circumstance, the predominant emotion is fear, which causes destructive thoughts for the student at a cognitive level, and for this reason, they decide not to participate. This is how it is identified that emotions have an impact on learning, especially for students. Therefore, in order to obtain relevant data regarding the emotions that students present, direct observation must be used. It is a technique used in various fields of knowledge, which involves the systematic collection of information about a given phenomenon or

situation through the perception and recording of data through the senses [2].

Currently there is a problem, because in the first hours of class, they have trouble paying attention, to which, they have reported that due to issues of nighttime recreational activities such as playing video games, using social networks and talking with their family, or that causes them to not sleep well, for this reason they are tired when they enter the first classes, this will result in students not learning the different subjects, causing a poor result in the subjects and this will cause the emotions of sadness, frustration, stress, tension and anxiety to have a negative impact on the individual, thus leading to regret causing irrational decision making.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

II. Emotional intelligence in the educational context

Studies conducted in Peru affirm that a recurring theme is the crisis that is being faced in the educational system, in response to which, he referred that a main cause lies in the lack of happiness of both teachers and students; in teachers, this unhappiness manifests itself as a lack of emotional control, motivation, depression and physical illnesses, and in students it manifests itself as a lack of interest, rebellion, attention and learning disorders, and violence. The author mentions that there are problems because the absence of emotional education in educational institutions generates negative consequences for students and the human community. Therefore, behavioral problems, violence and drug addiction.

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In the interpretation of the results it was concluded The solution is that working on emotional intelligence in a planned manner will yield beneficial results that contribute to emotional understanding and the judicious regulation of emotions that promote personal improvement. In this way, it would be important to include emotional skills in curriculum programming [3].

On the other hand, a study conducted in Bolivia showed that learning has an important relationship with motivations, which drive human learning. Motivations modulate the information received, generating a positive or negative disposition. It is then identified that an individual's actions are based on emotions; when a person changes feelings, they change their domain of action. Therefore, when there is a relationship between feelings and the classroom climate, they generate well-being in students and, consequently, allow for meaningful learning, as they promote self-esteem, social and professional development, and consequently improve learning [4].

Studies conducted in Oaxaca, Mexico, show that it is currently necessary to adapt pedagogical content to the specific needs of each student to obtain more and better academic results. Therefore, identifying a student's learning style contributes to improving their performance by providing activities tailored to individual interests. When these activities are related to an EI, a comprehensive outcome can be obtained for students, teachers, and administrative staff [5]. Emotional state can affect and/or benefit the quality of learning and the achievement of desired results. Therefore, it is important to recognize emotional states in the educational context, as it allows for the assignment of pedagogical content tailored to individual interests and preferences and, at the same time, for the evaluation of the effectiveness of the educational model. Thus, it was identified that students lacked awareness of emotional intelligence, resulting in conflicts with classmates, relationships with teachers, administrative and service staff, personal problems, difficulty speaking in public, expression of emotions, and mood swings, all of which negatively impact the academic environment by not fitting into work groups. The author concludes that Interpersonal Intelligence is most effective when there is less pressure and greater empathy, stress management, and harmonious social relationships. These aspects positively influence students' academic performance, as they feel motivated to learn and excel.

Likewise, the author concluded that the development of EI allows students to control emotions in a positive way, being aware of their own feelings and respecting those of others, showing empathy, and controlling impulses. This allows for better interrelation within working groups, achieving greater fluidity when determining group consensus, plenary sessions, workshops, and presentations.

Another relevant point is due to the research carried out in Coahuila, Mexico, where the authors comment that the pandemic had an impact on the emotional stability of higher

education, since the transformation of school and family roles were important factors of emotional impact and forced us to face new perspectives on learning barriers in the educational and family environment; given this situation, they related positive emotions to aspects such as technological self-learning, self-knowledge, among others [6].

Given this circumstance, a study was conducted in Sonora, Mexico, which explored emotional factors. These factors refer to the different ways in which students express their own emotions and recognize them in others. Therefore, a student may prefer a particular way of learning, which is directly related to their learning style [7].

The research seeks to identify the problem related to the impact of emotional intelligence on the learning process of students in the Information Technology areas at the Polytechnic University of Tulancingo. This is done to analyze whether EI favors the process of knowledge acquisition and its relationship with the environment.

Emotional intelligence (EI), as proposed by Reuven Bar-On [8], is crucial for understanding a subject's behavior in their environment. Therefore, discussing EI in these times has become a fundamental topic for those who understand that both the cognitive and emotional spheres must be developed simultaneously. Individuals can make decisions through reasoning and the feelings they perceive. Thus, it can be identified that for an individual to develop proper EI, it is advisable to apply Martin and Boeck's model of emotional competencies [9]. This model encompasses five different partial capacities as constituent elements of emotional competence. First, the individual must recognize their own emotions, that is, be able to assess and name them. In other words, they must become aware that only a person who knows how and why they feel can manage, moderate, and organize their emotions consciously.

The process of emotional development causes important changes in all the capacities that comprise emotional intelligence. These abilities combine with the hormones found in the female sex, such that women exhibit higher levels, leading to women being socially considered "more emotional" than men. The factors that cause the development of EI are socioeconomic status, cultural background, sexual activity, and interpersonal relationships [10].

Human beings manifest their behavior when they interact with the social world, so the type of behavior they express will depend on the context, since certain actions can be understood as correct for one scenario, but deficient for another.

At the same time, the external stimulus is referred to as a neutral incentive, which acquires the properties of triggering the same response in the individual [11]. This means that, depending on the stimulus, the individual will have reflexes, so it is understood that innate, or non-conditional, reflexes are triggered from the individual's birth by the physicochemical properties of the conditions that provoke a response in the subject. On the other hand, conditional reflexes are established

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gradually in the development of the person and are conditional because they depend on many conditions for their formation and maintenance.

An emotion is a reaction that generates neurochemical and hormonal changes and responses. Therefore, emotions are key to human survival and have developed throughout human evolution [12].

Feelings and emotions are necessary to cope with the various situations that may arise, making individuals more aware of identifying, recognizing, and expressing their own emotions and feelings, as well as those of others around them [13].

Learning is all the knowledge acquired from the things that happen in everyday life. Through these means, individuals acquire knowledge, skills, abilities, and aptitudes that, in turn, generate experience and, therefore, a broader ability to resolve conflicts. There are several theories surrounding this situation that explain the subject's acquisition of knowledge in their environment [14].

Thus, the hypothesis proposed was correlational, which posits a relationship between variables. Which is described below:

H_{A1}: Self-awareness, emotional control, self-motivation, interpersonal relationships, and emotional counseling positively impact the Emotional Intelligence of students in Information Technology programs at the Polytechnic University of Tulancingo (UPT).

III. METHODOLOGY

For this research, a quantitative approach will be used. This approach is characterized by the use of quantitative methods and techniques and involves measurement, sampling analysis, and statistical processing. It is an organized process for verifying assumptions; in the quantitative part, steps cannot be skipped; this is represented in Figure 1 [15].

To conduct this research, it is important to assess the emotional intelligence of students studying Information Technology at the Polytechnic University of Tulancingo, in order to identify its impact on the learning process through research.

This research used a quantitative, longitudinal approach. A standardized emotional intelligence test was also administered, covering the areas of self-awareness, emotional

control, self-motivation, interpersonal relationships, and emotional counseling.

IV. PARTICIPANTS

This research was conducted with 429 students studying Information Technology at the Polytechnic University of Tulancingo. The sample size was estimated a priori, with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% error. The formula shown in Figure 2 was applied.

$$n = \frac{\sigma N p q}{e^2 (N-1) + \sigma^2 p q}$$

Figure 2: Sample formula

Thus, the survey was applied to 381 students, which was administered in the 3 training cycles as follows: first training cycle, 144 students of the Information Technology careers with a representative percentage of 38%; second training cycle 125 students of the Computer Systems Engineering educational program which has a representative percentage of 33% and finally the third training cycle 121 students of the Computer Systems Engineering educational program with a representative percentage of 32%.

V. RESULTS

Based on the results obtained from the data collection instrument and the arithmetic mean, the items with the highest scores correspond to "Resolving conflicts" with 2.25; then "Showing understanding toward others" with 2.22; on the other hand, the items with the lowest mean values correspond to the questions "Establishing support groups" with 1.72; and "Thinking about negative feelings without becoming distressed" with 1.77.

Regarding the "Self-awareness" variable, aspects related to physical changes in their emotions, negative thoughts, self-talk, identifying when stimuli make them angry, when they feel defensive, the impact of their actions, and how to calm themselves were addressed. 62.5% of the students surveyed frequently engage in self-awareness in their daily activities. On the other hand, the "emotional management" variable identifies aspects such as acting productively in anxiety-inducing situations, the ability to calm down, and anger at others. Thus, 60.6% of those surveyed tend to manage their emotions frequently. Another relevant point is the results of the "Self-motivation" variable, which reveals characteristics such as the ability to get going, eliminate useless habits, and easily recover after a conflict situation. 52% of students are capable of motivating themselves to achieve better academic results.

The "interpersonal relationships" variable addresses the ability to communicate accurately, mediate conflicts, express feelings, and resolve conflicts. This means that 40.9% of the students surveyed can relate well to the people in their

environment; however, despite the low percentage, it can be seen as an area of opportunity. Finally, the emotional counseling variable addresses mood swings, building trust, and providing support, which are essential characteristics that will provide students with the necessary tools for success. Thus, 40.9% of those surveyed can contribute to their environment, considering that these skills can be enhanced and improved.

VI. DISCUSSION

This analysis reveals a world of possibilities for developing students' EI. Despite both negative and positive results, students have the ability to develop skills that contribute to personal growth and, therefore, impact EI, which will favor conflict resolution.

Among the most significant results is that students who have developed their EI demonstrate greater motivation and effective coping strategies, which favors their concentration and persistence in the face of conflict. This demonstrates that EI contributes to social and personal skills that strengthen learning in comprehensive environments.

Thus, this research demonstrates that EI plays a fundamental role in the learning process of students in the Information Technology area at the UPT. Through this, it was observed that students who frequently exercise emotional control, self-awareness, self-motivation, good interpersonal relationships, and the ability to provide emotional counseling achieve better academic results. Thus, EI not only influences emotional well-being but also academic performance.

However, there are areas of opportunity that must be addressed immediately. While the results were favorable on average, weaknesses have also been detected in areas such as self-awareness, emotional coping, and interpersonal relationships. It was observed that students have difficulty regulating their emotions in pressured situations, so they choose to abandon those contexts, leaving their goals unfulfilled.

Their lack of EI can impair decision-making, and when participating in class, they may choose to remain silent and not express their point of view, even if it is correct. In this circumstance, the predominant emotion is fear, which cognitively generates destructive thoughts for the student, which is why they decide not to participate.

In addition, the lack of emotional control prevents students from relating optimally to each other. When they fail to control their thoughts and feelings when expressing their concerns, they foster a hostile environment, as the words and tone they use are often less than assertive.

However, there are areas of opportunity that need to be addressed. While the overall EI average was high, weaknesses were detected in areas such as stress management and empathy in collaborative situations. Some students reported difficulty regulating emotions in pressured environments, which can affect decision-making and

interaction in group projects. This aspect is crucial, as technology careers demand interpersonal skills and resilience in changing environments. EI is a determining factor in enhancing student learning; however, it is important that they strengthen their intrapersonal skills through interventions aimed at stress management, empathy, decision-making, interpersonal relationships, and self-awareness. This is done through a mental health specialist, since in the academic context, students prefer to ask for support from a classmate, where, in most cases, they do not have the critical thinking skills to provide a favorable opinion.

VII. CONCLUSION

The most significant results of the quantitative phase of this research focus on the fact that emotional intelligence is a tool that contributes to the intrapersonal and interpersonal growth of students in their respective environments. Furthermore, it should be emphasized that self-awareness is the main tool that students must develop in order to foster a socio-affective culture among their academic, family, and social groups. It is also important to consider that students should seek psychological counseling where they can acquire more psychosocial tools for conflict resolution.

This research has generated several significant contributions regarding the relationship between emotional intelligence and the learning process in students of Information Technology programs at the Polytechnic University of Tulancingo. Therefore, despite the negative results regarding the way in which students can emotionally counsel their peers, this does not mean that they will not be able to perform this action; rather, it is an area of opportunity for them to become self-motivated and generate more tools to adapt to current needs. The most significant results of the quantitative phase of this research focus on the strengths of the educational organization, having as its greatest strength the performance of the administrative staff, this is important, due to the internal work carried out between the different departments, adequate communication, teamwork, and attention to the university community, which encourages achieving the institutional vision, and at the same time increases the work of the transformational leader.

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